

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14187651

Principals' Management Practices As Correlates Of Teachers' Job Commitment In Public Secondary Schools In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined principals' management practices as correlates teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted with a population of 6915 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 849 teachers was used for the study. Disproportionate stratified sampling techniques were used for the study. Three sets of instruments questionnaire "(PMPQ) Principals' Management Practices Questionnaire; and Teachers' job commitment questionnaire; were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method and the average coefficient values of 0.81 for PMPQ is considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for the study. Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The T-value was used to determine the significance of differences at .05 significant levels for all hypotheses. The results revealed that principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State, agreed that principals' management practices are correlates teachers' job commitment. From the results of the hypotheses, significant correlation was established in the responses of teachers on all the variables of the study. The study concluded that principals' management practices improves teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended that principals of public secondary school adopt innovative strategic finding initiatives for their schools that will involve accessing of funds from both the government and Private establishments through government collaborations. The study has contributed to knowledge by reviewing the imperativeness of adequate fund management since provision of adequate fund to the school principal helps in improving commitment of teachers.

Keyword: Principals' Management Practices and Teachers' Job Commitment.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an instrument for achieving socio-economic and technological growth and development in any nation. It is an instrument of excellence and the means of developing human intellect, technical skills, character, and effective citizenship for self-reliance and effective national development (FRN, 2014). Education, in essence, is the most effective tool for academic progress, social mobilization, political survival, and the effective national development of a country; it constitutes the single largest enterprise in Nigeria. The educational policy of any nation is to achieve Education for All (EFA). The priority is to ensure equitable access and improvement in the quality and efficiency of all levels of education. Therefore, it is typical for an educational institution to sufficiently provide for its clients (parents, students, society, employers of labour, and other stakeholders) through the teachers, who are the direct channels through which educational objectives can be transmitted to learners. The principal

is saddled with the task of overseeing the activities of students and teachers for the actualization of the educational objectives of the nation. However, for education to strive with the recent pace of development, the school principal needs to adopt practices that can help the school achieve optimal results and also improve teachers' job commitment.

Commitment can be seen as the process through which people become willing to give their loyalty and energy to a particular social system. Teachers' job commitment is the emotional bond between the teachers and the school. Ikedimma and Okorji (2023) averred that teachers' job commitment is teachers' identification with and involvement in a particular school. This commitment can be characterized by a strong personal belief in and acceptance of the school goals and values, a desire to exert oneself for the betterment of the school, and a strong will to remain with the school. It is the psychological identification of the individual teacher with the school and the intention of that teacher to maintain his membership of the school, and show all personal interest. One of the most important aspects in effective teaching has been identified as teacher job commitment (Altun, 2017). Teachers' job commitment is the dedication of teaching staff towards their duties. Okaforcha (2021) noted teachers' job commitment expresses the teachers' motivational orientation to the job in which they are engaged. Teachers' job commitment is their engagement in statutory obligations in the school. Similarly, Onafowo *et al.* (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as the willingness of teaching staff to put their efforts and time in performing their duties. Teachers who are committed to their job feel passionate about their duties and strive to excel in them. Nwogwugwu (2024) referred to teachers' job commitment as a physical, psychological and mental attachment to the demands of one's job.

Teachers' job commitment is the state of being loyal and devoted in executing instructional responsibilities in the school. High level of teachers' job commitment is essential for school success. Teachers with high level of commitment view themselves as integral part of the school, what threatens the school endangers them as well, they do their best to perform their duties better, and work for the school as if it belongs to them (Ikediugwu & Ibezim, 2023). In contrast, teachers with low level of commitment are less faithful to the school, view themselves as outsiders and are more concerned with personal success than with the success of the school as a whole.

Moreover, commitment ties an individual to the school in different ways and will differently affect the manner in which the employee conducts themselves in the workplace (Oforgbu, 2015). Fostering commitment among teachers is important because teachers, who are highly committed stay longer, perform better, actively involved in the work and engage in school citizenship behavior. Nyakan (2018) noted that teachers who express a higher level of commitment to the school, tend to voluntarily be absent from school less frequently. Similarly, Alsiewi and Agil (2018) believed that teachers with powerful job commitment find it easy to be interested in whatever is being carried out in the school and that the teachers can get involved wholeheartedly without strict supervision. Similarly, Nasir (2017) identified commitments in learning institutions as teachers' commitment to the institution, teachers' commitment to the students, teachers' commitment to the teaching occupation and commitment to outcomes. Furthermore, for teachers' optimal commitment to the school, their perception of principals' management practices is crucial.

Management practices is the process of evaluating; planning and implementing plans for the realization of school goals. Adeyemi (2018) explained that managerial practices involves systematic approach to making strategic decisions towards achieving strategic objectives. Management practices involves the formation and implementation of the major goals and initiatives, taken by a top management on behalf of owners, based on consideration of resources and assessment of the internal and external environments in which the organization competes. Similarly, Dornyei (2017) opined that management practices are motivational activities used by the principals in secondary schools in helping the teachers to ensure high productivity or high job performance. Management practices are the special abilities to administer the schools which are usually attributed to training and practice. In other words, management practices are set of behaviours that lead to effective job performance and without them in many cases the knowledge of school managers does not have any effect. Management practices are the principles that regulate our behaviour and ensure that the activities in school run smoothly. It refers to a system of rules of behaviour that ensures that things are done (Okafor, 2021).

Management practices can thus be described as a stream of decisions and actions which leads to the development of an effective strategy to help achieve educational objectives. However, School principal should put in place strategies that fosters creativity, generates new knowledge and concepts, expands the applicability of these ideas, and thereby serves as a foundation for innovation (Omur & Argon, 2016). Hence Voigt et al (2018) stated that management practices in schools involve funding, regulations, curricular flexibility, and availability of technology ready for use in an adequate professional development opportunity for teachers. According to Cunha and Magana (2019 pg.126), the term principals' management practices refer to the procedures, style and instructional techniques principals use to manage students' behavior and learning activities. Managerial strategies are the methods or techniques found to be the most effective and practical means in achieving an objective in secondary schools (Goodrich, 2015). Management practices initiated by the principal, who is the chief administrator of the school, are therefore designed to increase the output and efficiency of learning and to improve learning outcomes. Some of these practices, as stated by Amadi and Udisi (2021) are team building, strategic planning, and staff involvement practices that will enhance teachers' job performance. One factor that really needs to be taken into consideration is the strategies of the school management towards the teachers (Owence et al, 2018). Accordingly, Ekpo and Eze (2015) identify management practices as communication network, decision making, supervision, leadership, motivation, fund management, coordinating, staffing, planning, organizing, directing, evaluating and mediator between the school and community to ensure active job performance among teachers in secondary schools. Therefore, within the context of this study, the researcher focused on these aspect of principals management practices: fund management and motivation.

Fund Management practice by (Arinze & Ololube (2018) is critical to effective management of Secondary schools in Nigeria. Mifflin (2016) defined fund as a Sum of money or other resources that has been set aside for a specific purpose. Funds can take any of the following forms; physical cash, credit facilities such as trade credits or bank credits, allowances or discounts received and various expenses such as differentiable expenses like taxes, rent, bills, undistributed profit in the retained earnings, reserve, and so on (Arinze and Ololube, 2018) According to Titus and Ukaigwe (2018), fund management by school administrator requires managerial functions which deal with planning, acquisition and distribution of financial resources in order to achieve set Objectives in public Secondary schools. Moses (2014) averred that fund management practices like budgeting guarantees effectiveness of school administration by ensuring that only planned programmes are pursued, unnecessary spending is avoided and that all proposed expenditures are matched towards the expected revenue, leaving no room for deficit. Titus and Ukaigbe (2018) stated that fund management is a managerial strategy which ensures that resources are adequately provided to meet school goals. The principal gives direction to the quality and standard of teaching and learning in the school and decides the failure or success of it through effective supervision. As observed by Mohammed (2016), no school can succeed in a situation where a principal does not constantly check the work of his subordinate. Without supervision of instruction by principals of basic education schools, the products may not achieve the overall goals of higher learning. Effective supervision by principals is therefore necessary in order to enhance teachers job commitment. Another aspect of principals' management practices is motivation.

Motivation is key factor in enhancing teacher's commitment which in turn is an important determinant of specific learning outcomes. It is in this perspective that higher motivation leads to positive educational learning outcomes. Northouse (2016) states that when school principals exercises their managerial roles by motivating teachers, non-teachers, and students to realize their set goals, teachers feel motivated to teach and students feel motivated and encouraged to learn. Motivation is described as what makes an individual to follow certain ways where they direct their energies for sustainability (Fiumara, 2016). Motivation gives insight into what drives teachers to behave the way they do and spurs them to attain a goal. Motivation signifies a driving force, a kind of stimulus, an incentive or interest that spurs a teacher into action. Motivation recognizes that the achievement of individual objectives is instrumental to behaviour bearing on work performance. Motivation is one of the three factors in the function of directing is described as a process that arouses, channels, sustains and gives people's behavior purpose and direction It is an inner drive which prompts people to act in a certain way. Motivation involves a number of psychological factors

that starts and maintains activities toward the achievement of a personal or corporate goal. Motivation is the willingness to exhibit persistent and high level of effect toward organizational goals, conditioned by effort and ability to satisfy some individual needs”.

These management practices such as fund management and motivation works together to create effective school climate for change. Without motivated workforce, where principals are inexperienced and inappropriate managerial strategies prevailing, an organization could lose all that they have earned over the years. The implication of non-commitment to duty and the high rate of teacher attrition arising from poor job satisfaction have drawn increased attention from an array of perspective including education ministries and general society. Though seldom articulated, the interest in these trends centres on their consequences for the students. Job commitment of teachers has direct implications on the learners and the overall success of school as an organization. Within the Nigerian contemporary society, the education of youths is an issue of serious concern because it does not only ensure sustainable development but also makes for continued capacity building. While also the current argument on the influence of principals’ management practices on job commitment of teachers appear to be quite logical and coherent, it must also be appreciated that the argument is not backed up by empirical research data. As such, how principals’ management practices correlate job commitment among secondary school teachers in Anambra state is still in doubt and requires very urgent empirical research, hence the import of this present study.

Statement of the Problem

Education is a solid investment that is expected to enhance economic growth and development of individuals as well as the society as a whole. It is undeniable fact that education is a strong factor of social mobility which implies that education has the ability to influence a person’s future economic status in the society. Qualitative education is a determinant to national development and national integration as it is popularly said that “any nation that wants to grow should invest in education. Nevertheless, this growth and development cannot be achieved until there is adequate, sufficient and effective adoption of appropriate management practices by the school principals particularly at the level of Secondary Schools which is more or less the foundation level of education industry of any nation. There has been a recurring controversy bordering the minds of all stakeholders over the management practices of secondary schools across Anambra state. Amongst some of the key problems that confront the present research are that, there seems to be a prevalence of negative influence principals’ motivation process on teachers’ job commitment in secondary schools in Anambra State. Similarly, it has been noted that there are poor principals’ fund management practice, poor communication practice and poor supervision practice on teachers’ job commitment in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. These key problems have negatively impacted on the quality of secondary school service delivery across all schools in the state which this study seeks to investigate.

It is against this backdrop therefore, and in the light of these distasteful circumstances, that this study raises this question: what is the relationships between principals’ management practices with teachers’ job commitment in in public schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine if principals management practices correlate with teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary School in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

8. examine the relationship between fund management practice and teachers job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.
9. establish the relationship between motivation practice and teachers job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

5. What is the relationship between fund management practice and teachers job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?
6. What is the relationship between motivation practice and teachers job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

- d) There is no significant relationship between fund management practice and teachers job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- e) There is no significant relationship between motivation practice and teachers job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design for this study. The area of the study is Anambra state. There six educational zone in Anambra State which are Aguata, Awka, Nnewi, Ogidi, Onitsha and Otuocha. The population of the study comprised 6915 teachers as respondents. The sample size is 849 teachers drawn using Disproportionate stratified random sampling technique. Two instruments were used for data collection. The first instruments was a self-structured questionnaire, titled “Principals’ Management Practices’ Questionnaire (PMPQ)”, while the second instrument titled “Teachers’ Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ) was adopted. PMPQ which contain 20 items is made of two sections namely; A and B. Section A which focused on fund management contains 10 items, and section B contained 10 items on motivation. On the other hand, TJCQ contains 20 items. All the items in two instruments were structured on four point rating scale with response format of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) and numerical value of 4,3,2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts two from Educational Management and one from Educational Measurement and Evaluation, all from Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents with the help of six research assistants. A total number of 480 were retrieved which represented 80% return rate and 20% loss.

The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha formula and average coefficient values 0.81 for PMPQ is considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of 0.05 the null hypotheses was accepted.

PRESENATION OF RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between fund management practice and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Pearson (r) on Relationship between Fund Management Practice and Teachers’ Job Commitment.

		Correlation		Fund Management	Teachers job Commitment	Remark
Fund Management	Pearson Correlation	Sig.(2-tailed)	1	.888**	.000	
	N		86	86		
Teachers’ job commitment	Pearson Correlation	Sig.(2-tailed)	.888**	.000	1	Strong positive relationship
	N		86	86		

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

Analysis from Table 1 showed that there is a strong positive relationship between fund management and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is as a result of the 'r' being positive with the value $r = 0.888$ and $N = 86$. Thus, the study concluded that there exists a strong positive relationship between fund management and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between motivation practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Pearson(r) on Relationship between Motivation Practice and Teachers' Job Commitment.

Correlation				Motivation practice	Teachers job Commitment	Remark
Motivation strategy	Pearson tailed)	Correlation	Sig.(2-tailed)	1	.501**	
	N			86	86	
Teachers' job commitment	Pearson tailed)	Correlation	Sig.(2-tailed)	.501**	1	Moderate positive correlation
	N			86	86	

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

Analysis from Table 2 showed that there is a moderate positive relationship between motivation practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is as a result of the 'r' being positive with the value $r = 0.501$ and $N=86$. Thus, the study concluded that there exists a moderate positive relationship between motivation practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between fund management strategy and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 3: Summary of t-test of significant Relationship between Fund management Practice and Teachers' Job Commitment

Correlation				Fund management Practice	Teachers job Commitment	Decision
Fund management Practice	Pearson tailed)	Correlation	Sig.(2-tailed)	1	.888**	
	N			86	86	
Teachers' job commitment	Pearson tailed)	Correlation	Sig.(2-tailed)	.888**	1	Significant
	N			86	86	

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

The result of the test of significance of Pearson-Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 3 above showed a significant relationship between fund management practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State with $r = 0.888$. $N = 86$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.00$. Since $p\text{-value} 0.000$ is less than 0.05 , the study rejects the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a significant relationship between fund management practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State .

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between motivation practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test of significant Relationship between Motivation Practice and Teachers' Job Commitment

				Correlation			
				Motivation Strategy	Teachers job Commitment	Decision	
Motivation Practice	Pearson tailed)	Correlation	Sig.(2-	1	.501**		
	N			86	0.00		
Teachers' job commitment	Pearson tailed)	Correlation	Sig.(2-	.501**	1	Significant	
	N			86	0.00		

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

The result of the test of significance of Pearson-Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 4 above showed a significant relationship between motivation practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State with $r=0.501$. $N = 86$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.00$. Since $p\text{-value} 0.000$ is less than 0.05 , the study rejects the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a significant relationship between motivation practice and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION

Finding on the relationship between fund management practice and teacher job commitment in public secondary school in Anambra State revealed that principals are in accordance that there is strong positive relationship between fund Management and teachers' Job commitment. The analysis also shows that there is significant relationship between fund Management and Teachers' job commitment. Therefore, the two results show that School Principals in public secondary Schools in Anambra state accept that there is positive relationship between fund management and teachers' job commitment. The Idea behind this is that the respondents appreciate knowing how to evaluate the school financial resources for administrative effectiveness. The respondents also admit that involving competent staff in managing the schools financial resources will enhance teachers' job commitment.

This may have resulted because funds are essential part of the school resources. The availability and effective utilization of funds would improve the level of Instant Infrastructural Provision and resources in the school leading to teachers job commitment. Finding is in agreement with Amirize and Ololube (2018) who reported that there are significant relationships between principals fund management strategies, accountability, factors that hinder, and factors that strengthens an effective administration of secondary schools. In the Same vein, Titus and Ukaigwe (2018) stated that fund management will to a large extent lead to Improvement in the administration of secondary schools. In the same vein, Uzoigwe (2013) noted that funding of secondary schools will ensure administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools.

Furthermore, finding revealed a significant correlation between fund management strategy and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding indicates that funds would improve the teachers' Job Commitment of public Secondary schools. This is in line with Amirize and Ololube (2018) who found that fund management practice improves teachers' job commitment.

Finding on the relationship between motivation practice and teacher job commitment in public secondary school in Anambra State revealed that there was moderate relationship between motivation practice of principals and Teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State this was in line with the finding of Nweneka (2019) which revealed that there was a moderate positive correlation between teachers' motivation and their job Commitment. This possible explanation for the agreement. In the findings could be attributed to the fact that the studies were conducted in secondary schools in the same country and utilized teachers as the participants. Motivational Strategies of principals were a moderate Correlation of teachers' job commitment, it boosted their Morale and

dedication to their duties. Motivated teachers are punctual to school, dedicated to their daily duties and work harder to bring about an increase in their job commitment or performance. The motivational practices of principals served as incentive which made teachers more enthusiastic about their duties and put more efforts to improve their job performance.

It was also revealed that there was significant relationship between staff motivational practices of principals and Teachers Job Commitment in public secondary Schools in Anambra State. This finding agreed with that of Masifa and Hassan (2022) which showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between Motivational practices and Teachers Job Commitment. This was in disagreement with the finding of Komolafe and Gbotosho (2019) which indicated that there was a significant relationship between motivation and Teachers' job Commitment of staff. The Significant relationship that existed between staff motivational strategy of principals and Teachers' job Commitment could be attributed to the fact that when teachers are motivated, they could be willing to work harder to achieve exceptional job Commitment in the workplace. Motivated teachers carry out their responsibilities to the highest standard to attain better job Commitment.

CONCLUSION

This study findings showed that principals' management practices determined the level of teachers' job' commitment. Also the extent to which teachers' are motivated to work extra hours attending to students' needs and preferring solutions to students' problems depends largely on the effective management practices adopted by the school principals. Therefore, principals' management practices are absolutely necessary in any academic settings for adequate teacher job commitment. The application of the management practices explored in this study will lead to improvement in the administrative process of public secondary schools. It is therefore pertinent for school principals and other school, administrators to seek out ways to improve their management abilities so to improve the quality of the administrative teaching, learning and teachers' job commitment in secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher made the following recommendations;

1. Principals of public secondary school adopt innovative strategic finding initiatives for their schools that will involve accessing of funds from both the government and Private establishments through government collaborations.
2. Principals should adopt motivational practices which will boost staff and teachers morale in public secondary schools.

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